

DIRECTIONALITY OF THERMAL EXPANSION BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERLAMINAR THERMAL STRESSES.

T.D. Le* and D.J. Chang**

Mechanics and Materials Technology Center

*Structural Materials Department, ** Mechanics & Propulsion Department

THE AEROSPACE CORPORATION

P.O. Box 92957

Los Angeles, CA 90009-2957

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is two-fold: (1) to characterize the directionality of the thermal expansion behavior of unidirectional P100S/6061 metal matrix composite and (2) to determine the interlaminar stresses induced by thermal mismatch in a multi-ply laminate. This was accomplished by using the laser interferometry technique to study the thermal expansion behavior along various orientations relative to the fiber direction, specifically 0°, 10°, 30°, 45°, 75°, and 90°. The thermal expansion and contraction of the sample was monitored continuously throughout a complete thermal cycle of RT → +70°C → -30°C → RT. Along each orientation, the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) and thermal hysteresis that were used exhibited a remarkable difference in behavior and magnitude. The direction-dependent CTEs of the laminae were incorporated in classical lamination theory calculations to determine the temperature-induced interlaminar stresses in a cross-ply laminate.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite materials are being considered for use in a number of space structures where the dimensional stability is of primary importance. Examples include communication antennae, telescopes, and solar reflectors. Composites are leading candidates for these applications due to their high specific stiffnesses and low thermal expansion coefficients (CTE) in the fiber direction. In the space environment, these structures may experience cyclic thermal loading over the temperature range -157°C to 121°C in the high-earth orbit or -30°C to 70°C in the low-earth orbit.

In a uni-directional (UD) composite, due to the anisotropic thermal properties of reinforcing fibers, the thermal expansion behavior of UD composites are also anisotropic showing that the CTE of composites is dependent not only on the temperature but also on the direction away from the fiber. Therefore, besides the microscopic, local thermal stresses at the fiber/matrix interface induced by the differential CTE between the fiber and matrix. This non-uniform thermal expansion will consequently lead to the development of macroscopic thermal stresses within a composite. These thermal stresses are the cause of the warping problem, transverse cracks, and

delamination within a multi-ply laminates during thermal cycling or processing. Although transverse cracking may not significantly alter the structural integrity of a laminate, the thermal expansion behavior may change significantly, in addition with warping, to render the laminate unacceptable for dimensional stability critical applications.

The purpose of the present study was to investigate the development of macroscopic thermal stresses within a uni-directional composite plate and a cross-ply laminate under pure thermal loading conditions. This was accomplished by dividing the study in two parts. First, the thermal expansion behavior of uni-directional composite was characterized along the fiber direction and off-axis directions forming different angles with respect to the reinforcing fibers. This characterization was performed over a typical range of temperature of which a material is subjected to in low earth orbit. Despite of the considerable work[1-5] devoted to thermal expansion and thermal stress problems, the current elastic analysis methods do not provide a general basis for formulating a prediction for such behavior as changing in CTE of a composite with temperature due to the plastic flow of the matrix that causes thermal hysteresis. Therefore, in the second part, the CTE values obtained from a single unidirectional lamina were used to determine the evolution of the macroscopic thermal stress in a composite plate under thermal cycling conditions through the use of classical laminate plate theory. An example of such a laminate is a plate composed of a series of angle-ply systems stacked symmetrically with respect to the central plane. The calculation of interlaminar stresses was based solely on the measured mechanical and thermal expansion properties of a unidirectional lamina. Calculations of this type will have technological significance as they specify the material parameters and geometric construction necessary to yield structural elements with zero or minimal expansion coefficients and interlaminar stresses.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials & Specimens

Unidirectional Gr/Al composite was used in this study. The fibers are P100S and the matrix is 6061 aluminum alloy. The composite panel was manufactured by melt-infiltration technique and received in as-casted conditions. The composite plate was microstructurally inspected at several different locations and found to be of good quality, uniform metal penetration. The fiber volume fraction is approximately 52% by quantitative metallography. Table I listed the properties of the constituents. Specimens were cut at angles of 0°, 10°, 30°, 45°, 75°, and 90° with respect to the fiber direction as depicted in Fig. 1. Typical size is 76.2 mm x 19.0 mm x thickness (1.33 mm). The cutting was performed with great care using a diamond saw blade to avoid any damage.

Thermal Deformation Characterization

The thermal expansion behavior of the samples were characterized in-house using the Michelson Laser Interferometer in the Dimensional Stability Laboratory, a state-of-the-art technology[6, 7] capable of μ -strain resolution and accuracy which is essential in studying the thermal expansion behavior of advanced composites with CTE values as low as $10^{-8}/K$. This technique provides in-situ, direct, continuous measurements of thermal expansion/contraction through a thermal cycle without recourse to a comparative standard. Figure 2 shows a sketch of the set-up of the laser interferometry system. A He-Ne laser is used as the laser source which provides a coherent, stable single frequency beam. The beam is split by a beam splitter. One beam is directed to a mirror (PZT) and deflected straight down into the vacuum chamber to a mirror (working mirror) mounted on top of the sample. The other beam is deflected directly from the beam splitter to a

reference mirror on which the sample is erected. The reflected beams from the reference and working mirrors retrace along their respective paths, go through the optical system and adjusted to overlap. The interference of two reflected beams forms a fringe pattern. Sample expansion or contraction will cause a shift in fringe pattern. Each shift corresponds to a change in sample dimension equal to one half the wave length of the laser. The sense of shifting in the fringe pattern due to thermal expansion or contraction is detected by two photo-detectors. The signals from the two photo-detectors are fed through a oscilloscope and a laser tracking system to track the sense of dimensional change and convert the digital signals to analog. The analog outputs in mV are plotted on a strip chart along with the output of thermocouples that monitor sample temperature. Two chromel-alumel thermocouples were mounted on both sides of the specimen to monitor the temperature change. In all cases, thermal cycling was carried out by heating the sample first from room temperature (RT) to the hot end of the cycle, and then cooling down to the cold end and finally heating back up to RT. The selected temperature range was from -30°C to $+70^{\circ}\text{C}$, typical temperature range under which a material is subjected in the low earth orbit. The heating and cooling rate was closely controlled to $\sim 1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. to ensure thermal equilibrium throughout the entire sample. The thermal strain data were plotted against temperature to produce graphs showing the thermal expansion behavior of a sample through a complete thermal cycle as shown in Figs. 3 through 5.

Interlaminar Stress Calculations

In the present study, we consider a case of symmetrical 8-ply laminate with the lay-up angle of $(0^{\circ}, \pm 45^{\circ}, 90^{\circ})_s$. The interlaminar stress in the composite laminate were calculated by using the theory of composite laminates [7, 8]. Since the laminate considered in this work is symmetric, we assumed that there are no bending stresses induced as a result of thermal excursion. Also, the calculation is pseudo-elastic. For cases where yielding occurred, a modulus value lower than 69.8 GPa was used. This modulus value was derived from the corresponding CTE in the temperature range of interest. The evolution of interlaminar stresses was determined corresponding to the change of CTE in different spans of temperature during a thermal cycle as shown in Fig. 3. Therefore, the magnitude of stress at each stage is the summation of the stresses calculated for each preceding temperature ranges.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 3, it is evident from the thermal expansion behavior of the 0° sample that when sample was heated from RT, initially, fibers and matrix behaved elastically, and the composite expanded from A to B with the CTE determined by the rule of mixture. As heating continued to the temperature of 55°C or above, differential thermal expansion eventually brought the matrix to the compressive yield stress and the thermal expansion became dominant by the fibers producing a plateau from B to C as observed. It is believed that upon continuing heating to a higher temperature, the composite's behavior will be completely dominant by the fibers' and contract with a CTE equal to that of the reinforcing fibers as indicated in the cooling section EF. Throughout the path from B to C, the matrix was yielding in compression. Upon cooling from point C (70°C), the composite unloaded and became fully elastic again with the fibers expanding, the matrix contracting until point D (40°C), the matrix began to flow plastically again. Beyond point D, the composite's behavior, again controlled by the fibers, expanded with decreasing temperature until point F. As a logical continuation, the composite went through the same process upon heating from -30°C to RT and completed a loop with a hysteresis of $\sim 50 \mu\text{-strain}$. The sample length, however, did not return to its original position creating a permanent offset of $\sim 35 \mu\text{-strain}$. It is noted that the matrix is in as-casted condition with the YS of about 48 to 55

Mpa, the matrix, therefore, yielded earlier at lower temperature than compared to the same matrix heat treated at T6 condition. This loop was obtained after first cycle, experience has shown that continuing thermal cycling will yield loops with the total strain range increases with each successive cycle, while the width of the hysteresis loop progressively decreases until the stability is obtained. This occurs because strain hardening strengthened the matrix after each cycle delaying the yielding to a higher temperature, decreasing the amount of plastic strain associated with each cycle, and as a consequence, resulting in a narrower hysteresis loops. It is obvious that the CTE varies over different spans of temperature and their average values are listed in association with the plot. These values were used in the classical lamination theory calculations to determine the development of interlaminar stresses with changing temperature throughout a complete cycle.

Thermal strain versus temperature plots of 10° off-axis and transverse samples are shown in Figs. 4 and 5. The thermal expansion behavior of 10° sample shown in Fig. 4, demonstrates the same features of thermal hysteresis and permanent offset as in the case of 0° . However, the predominant effects of the fibers is not observed here as in the 0° case. The sample expanded and contracted with temperature throughout the cycle. The reverse trend in thermal behavior due to plastic flow of the matrix is not observed. However, from the slope of the heating and cooling curves, one could see that if the sample was heated further beyond 70°C or cooled below -30°C , the induced thermal stresses will be large enough to cause plastic flow in the matrix and the fibers become dominant again and reverse trend occurs. The thermal expansion behavior of 30° to 90° off-axis samples is largely similar and self-consistent as typically shown in Fig. 5, with increasing off-axis angle leading generally to increasing CTE. In contrast to the behavior of the 0° and 10° samples illustrate the constraining effect that negative-CTE reinforcement have upon a positive CTE matrix. In all cases of off-axis angle greater than and equal to 30° , the thermal mismatch between the fiber and matrix becomes less and less, both phases expand and contract elastically, tracing along the same path leading to a zero thermal hysteresis. The implication of the results is that for the range of temperature employed in this study, at a certain angle away from the fiber direction, thermal expansion behavior of composite becomes linear and controlled by the rule of mixture. The plastic flow caused by the axial thermal mismatch between the fiber and the matrix have little effect upon the linearity.

The results of the unidirectional composite clearly indicate that under pure thermal loading, the thermal expansion in a composite plate is not uniform. This is best summarized in Fig. 6 showing the thermal expansion behavior of all angles. The non-uniform thermal expansivity is believed to be the origin of thermal residual stresses in metal matrix fiber composites. The mismatch of thermal strain along various orientation between two adjacent lamina induces and changes the pattern of internal stress in a composite laminate. This could arise in the processing and application of the material. In the present study, we consider a case of symmetrical 8-ply laminate with the lay-up angle of $(0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ)$. During a thermal cycle, the evolution of interlaminar stresses throughout a cycle was calculated and plotted in Fig. 7. Because of the symmetry of the lay-up structure of the selected laminate, the calculated interlaminar stresses between any layer are the same. Upon heating from room temperature, the interlaminar stress increases with temperature from zero to -9 Mpa (1305 psi) when temperature reached the hot end of the cycle. Upon cooling, the interlaminar stress decreases with temperature to -5.6 Mpa (811 psi) when temperature reached the cold end and increases again with temperature to -0.2 Mpa (29 psi) when heating back up to RT. The results clearly show that during thermal cycling, each layer is subjected to tension-compression thermal fatigue. The stresses plotted in Fig. 7 was not accounted for the residual stresses induced within the composite laminate upon cooling from high temperature during the preparation process of the composite, for example hot pressing. Potentially, the residual stresses are very high and when they combined with the cyclical stresses shown in Fig. 7, the effective stresses within a laminate could be large enough to cause delamination or transverse cracking of the material with increasing number of cycles.

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal expansion behavior of P100S/6061 unidirectional composite was characterized along various orientation relative to the fiber direction. The CTE increases progressively with off-axis angle from near-zero along the fiber direction to a high value ($20.6 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) along the transverse direction. Along the fiber direction and 10° off-axis sample, the composite exhibited strain hysteresis and a residual plastic strain after the first cycle in the temperature range. In contrast, along off-axis angles 30° , the thermal expansion behavior is linear with zero thermal hysteresis. Overall, the results indicate that under pure thermal loading, the thermal expansion and contraction within a unidirectional composite plate is not uniform. Based on the CTE results obtained in the unidirectional composite plate, calculations were performed to determine the interlaminar stresses in a cross-ply laminate. The results indicate that during thermal cycling, each layer in the laminate is subjected to tension-compression thermal fatigue. These cyclic stresses combined with a residual stresses existing in composites are believed to be the main force in inducing warping and delamination within a laminate during thermal cycling or processing.

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Table I. Material Properties

<u>P100S Fibers</u>		<u>6061 Matrix</u>	
$E_{11} = 724 \text{ GPa}$	$E_{22} = 9.93 \text{ GPa}$	$E = 68.97 \text{ GPa}$	$G = 26.21 \text{ GPa}$
$G_{12} = 19.93$	$GPa \nu_{12} = 0.41$	$\nu = 0.33$	$\alpha = 22.3 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
$\alpha_1 = -1.1 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$	$\alpha_t = 21.6 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$		

Fig. 1. Lay-out of testing angles.

Fig. 2. Laser interferometry set-up.

Figs. 3 - 5. Thermal expansion behavior of 0°, 10°, and transverse sample.

P100S/6061 (All Angles)

Fig. 6. Thermal expansion behavior of all samples.

Fig. 7. Graph showing the change of interlaminar stress with temperature during a thermal cycle.